

Mixed Ligand Complexes of Bis(Acetylacetonato) Nickel(II) with Urea and Thioureas

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Bis(acetylacetonato) nickel(II) has been reacted in ethanolic medium with urea, thiourea, N-ethylthiourea, N,N'-diethylthiourea, N-phenylthiourea and N,N'-diphenylthiourea and six spin-free, non-electrolytic, octahedral, mixed-ligand complexes having a general composition, $[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2\text{L}_2]$, have been isolated and characterised. The infra-red spectral data indicate the presence of both acetylacetonato and the hetero ligands in the complexes. The electronic spectra in acetone medium indicate distorted octahedral structure for these complexes.

SEVERAL mixed ligand complexes of nickel(II) containing β -diketones and nitrogen¹⁻³ and oxygen^{4,5} donor ligands have been reported earlier. It was thought worthwhile to undertake the study of the complexes formed between bis(acetylacetonato) nickel(II) and urea (u), thiourea (tu), N-ethylthiourea (Et.tu), N,N'-diethyl-thiourea (Et₂tu), N-phenyl thiourea (ϕ .tu) and N,N'-diphenyl thiourea (ϕ_2 .tu).

Experimental

The compounds were isolated¹ as before from warm ethanolic medium. The complexes containing N-phenylthiourea and N,N'-diphenylthiourea needed refluxing for 15 min. The compounds were filtered, washed with ethanol and ether, and dried *in vacuo*.

The purity of the isolated compounds was established by estimating the metal content. The molar conductance measurements were made in acetone medium using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made over solid specimens using Gouy method. The infra-red spectra were recorded as nujol mulls using a double beam Unicam SP-200 spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra were recorded from acetone solution (10^{-2} M) using Unicam SP-500 spectrophotometer.

The characterisation data and the infra-red and electronic spectral data have been given in Tables 1-3.

Results and Discussion

$[\text{Ni}(\text{dik})_2]$, where Hdik = acetylacetonato, benzoyl-acetonato and dibenzoylmethane have been isolated in hydrated and anhydrous forms. The hydrated forms are octahedral in structure having two water molecules situated at trans positions. The anhydrous forms are either square-planar or attain octahedral

configuration by trimerization^{2,3} in the presence of non-interacting solvents. In the presence of donor solvents, the polymerization is lifted³ with the formation of mixed ligand complexes in the ratios of 2 : 1 and 1 : 2 $[\text{Ni}(\text{dik})_2$: ligand].

All the compounds reported here have the composition $[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2\text{L}_2]$ where Hacac = acetylacetonato and L = urea, thiourea, N-ethylthiourea, N,N'-diethylthiourea, N-phenylthiourea or N,N'-diphenyl thiourea. The values of low molar conductance (Λ_M) for these compounds (Table 1) indicate that they are non-electrolytes. All the compounds are paramagnetic with μ_{eff} values ranging between 3.02 and 3.21 B.M. which are within the range for octahedral complexes of nickel(II)⁶. These compounds are, therefore, spin-free octahedral complexes.

Infra-red spectra of the starting material, $[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ and the products have been taken which show that the band due to co-ordinated water molecules at ~ 3510 cm^{-1} in $[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ is absent in the products. The i.r. bands of important vibrations of both acetylacetonato and the hetero-donor molecules have been given with relevant assignments in Tables 2 and 3.

The changes in $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ which occur round about 450 cm^{-1} fall beyond the range of the instrument used. The absorption due to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{C})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ undergoes slight shifts (Table 3). The direction and the amount of these shifts can not be correctly predicted since there will always be a metal-ligand π -linkage superimposed on a $\text{L} \rightarrow \text{M}$ σ -bond.

The bands of both acetylacetonato and the hetero ligands have been modified which indicate that both of them are bonded to the metal ion. Since there are examples of thiourea being bonded to the metal ion either through S- or N-atoms, the infra-red response of the important modes have been evaluated in Table 2. According to Bailey and Pearson⁷ and

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TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, MELTING POINT, MAGNETIC MOMENT AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF BIS (ACETYLACETONATO) NICKEL(II) WITH UREA AND THIOUREA

Compound	Colour and form	Melting Point (°C)	% Nickel		% Sulphur		μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Λ_M (mhos) (in acetone)
			Reqd.	Obsd.	Reqd.	Obsd.		
1. Ni(acac) ₂ (u) ₂	green, crystalline	250	15.55	15.38	—	—	3.21	12.8
2. Ni(acac) ₂ (tu) ₂	green, microcrystalline	160d	14.37	14.22	15.66	15.32	3.09	5.8
3. Ni(acac) ₂ (Et.tu) ₂	green, amorphous	150d	12.63	12.38	13.77	13.39	3.14	4.5
4. Ni(acac) ₂ (Et ₂ tu) ₂	light green, amorphous	240d	11.28	11.07	12.29	12.21	3.13	3.9
5. Ni(acac) ₂ (ϕ .tu) ₂	green, microcrystalline	163d	10.47	10.43	11.42	11.28	3.02	8.5
6. Ni(acac) ₂ (ϕ_2 tu) ₂	grey, microcrystalline	176d	8.24	8.32	8.98	8.75	3.05	7.7

d = decomposed.

TABLE 2—IMPORTANT I.R. ABSORPTION BANDS OF THIOUREA AND SUBSTITUTED THIOUREA LIGANDS AND THEIR SHIFTS ON BONDING TO METAL IN Ni(acac)₂L₂ (IN CM⁻¹)

Compounds	ν (N-H)	$\Delta\{\nu$ (N-H)}	δ (NH ₂)	$\Delta\{\delta$ (NH ₂)}	Amide II vibrn.	Δ (Amide II vibrn.)
Tu	3120, 3220, 3320	+40 to +60	1610	-3	—	—
Ni(acac) ₂ (tu) ₂	3170, 3280, 3360		1607		—	
Et.tu	3145, 3220, 3320	+35 to +40	1615	0	1525	+15
Ni(acac) ₂ (Et.tu) ₂	3180, 3260, 3320		1615		1540	
Et ₂ tu	3250	+50	—	—	—	—
Ni(acac) ₂ (Et ₂ tu) ₂	3300		—		—	
ϕ .tu	3240, 3335	+75	1623	+2	1625	+15
Ni(acac) ₂ (ϕ .tu) ₂	3410		1625		1640	
ϕ_2 tu	3220, 3400	+10	—	—	1555	+11
Ni(acac) ₂ (ϕ_2 tu) ₂	3210, 3410		—		1566	

others^{8,9}, large increase in ν (N-H), and amide II vibrations and small shifts in the δ (NH₂) vibrations indicate S-bonding. The results shown in Table 2 are in conformity with this and indicate bonding of the thioureas to the metal through S-atom.

range of the spectrophotometer used and ν_3 band is obscured by the intense charge-transfer bands. The ν_2 bands along with the molar extinction coefficient (ϵ) are given in Table 3. In case of the complex, containing, N,N'-diphenylthiourea the value for ϵ is high but in all other cases it remains within 20 as expected for an octahedral coordination. Besides the main peak (ν_2), there are number of very weak peaks in the absorption spectrum which are presumably due to tetragonal distortion in the molecule as suggested¹⁰ earlier.

TABLE 3—INFRA-RED AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF THE MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF BIS(ACETYLACETONATO) NICKEL(II)

Compounds	ν (C-C) (cm ⁻¹)	ν (C-O) (cm ⁻¹)	ν_2 (m μ)	ϵ
Ni(acac) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	1603	1515	—	—
Ni(acac) ₂ (u) ₂	1597	1520	632	11.7
Ni(acac) ₂ (tu) ₂	1580	1500	630	9.3
Ni(acac) ₂ (Et.tu) ₂	1602	1518	635	10.8
Ni(acac) ₂ (Et ₂ tu) ₂	1607	1523	627	20.0
Ni(acac) ₂ (ϕ .tu) ₂	1590	1518	625	15.8
Ni(acac) ₂ (ϕ_2 tu) ₂	1587	1518	630	48.0

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The absorption spectra of these complexes have been recorded from their acetone solutions (10⁻² M) in the visible region. The ν_1 band falls outside the

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